

PHYSIOTHERAPY DURING PREGNANCY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6568289>

Ikromova Ziyoda

To'raxonova Oydin

Teachers of the Technical College of Public Health

named after Abu Ali ibn Sino

Abstract: *Therapeutic physical training is widely used in gynecological practice. Special exercises during pregnancy improve blood circulation, metabolic processes, respiratory and digestive system functions.*

Proper breathing of the future mummy contributes to the oxygenation of the blood and the saturation of the fetus in oxygen. In addition, exercise therapy increases the flexibility of muscles and ligaments, eliminates stagnant events in the legs and small pelvis, helps to strengthen the muscles of the pelvic cavity.

Exercise methods

From the first week of the week, a pregnant woman is constantly taught reading skills, including proper breathing and exercise. Gymnastics strengthens the musculoskeletal system, respiratory and cardiovascular systems during this pregnancy.

Gymnastics is designed to improve the conditions for normal fetal development from 17 weeks to 32 weeks, strengthening the perineal and abdominal muscles.

Gymnastics is aimed at maintaining the functional capabilities of the systems that ensure fetal growth and development at 32 weeks of gestation.

Gymnastics includes recovery exercises for the legs, trunk, arms. Special and breathing exercises to strengthen the legs, abdomen, back muscles. There are also exercises that help expand the perineum.

To strengthen the abdominal tissue, perform the following exercises: When we are in the starting position (PI), we do the nose and twist of the body. We run on our backs, imitating a bicycle, crossing our legs (like scissors), lifting our legs, and writing numbers with our legs straight up. To increase permeability of the perineum, perform exercises with maximum flexion, flexing the legs, increasing the size of the knees, and gathering the soles.

Approximate sets of exercises

The first complex

Weeks 17-32 Exercise begins with a slow walk. Breathing should be uniform and free (2 min). The sides raise their hands to the plant, lift up, stand on their toes, inhale, return to the FE, we breathe (repeat up to 6).

The arms across the torso, the shoulder width of the legs separated. We turn the body to the right, spread our chest wide to the chest, breathe in, return to the Fe, we breathe (3-4 times in each direction).

When you lie on your back, lift the fluids up, inhale, return to the FE, inhale, lie on your back, and exhale (6 times). Hold your feet for 30 seconds. Imitate cycling. Then 30 seconds. We make crossed leg movements (imitation of scissors), lift one leg, take it aside and return it to the FE (3-4 rubles with each leg). Breathe slowly and deeply (up to 8).

We ascend in the “net”. We lift the left side forward and our right leg is rotated - inhale, return to Fe, we inhale. Now the right arm forward, the left leg back (6 times).

We run on our knees, sit on our knees, breathe, stand on our knees, and exhale (eight times).

The second complex

32-40 weeks of exercise (weak group). Walking slowly on the road. Breathing should be the same (2 min). We raise the arms in torsion across the width of the shoulders, return the left arm, inhale, return to the FE, and exhale. We switch hands and repeat the exercise (4 d). The arms and legs are common - breathing, leaning to the right, raising the right arm, breathing, returning to the FE, breathing (three r on each side).

Our feet are placed on the floor and our feet are placed on the floor - breathing, lifting the pelvis, drawing on the anus, exhaling, returning FE-breathing, we lie down as we breathe.

He lies on his back, his legs straight, his arms under his head - breathing, his legs up - breathing. Inhale - we spread our legs to the sides, inhale - shorten our legs, inhale - lower our legs, leave our breath behind (4-6 r).

Lying next to him. We move the right foot and right hand to the breathing side, to the breathing IP. We practice every 4-6 r.

Standing on all fours - breathing, shortening our backs, lowering our heads, pushing us back, and raising our heads up - breathing (repeat up to 6).

REFERENCES:

1. M.F.Ziyayeva. Z.O.Rizayeva. “Bolalarda hamshiralik parvarishi”. Toshkent, “Fan va texnologiya” 2012 yil.
2. X.N Fayziyev. « Сестринский уход за детьми » Toshkent, «Илм ziyo» nashriyoti, 2008 yil
3. K.S Inomov. «Pediatriyada hamshiralik ishi» Toshkent, 2007 yil
4. www.ziyonet.uz
5. <https://mymedic.uz/>

